

Happy New Year!

Hello and welcome to the first LNL newsletter of 2024. Let's leap right in. We spotlight open research within the University of Liverpool and we have lots of opportunities for you to learn and engage in open research activities and events. And don't forget to nominate someone for a 'Doscar'.

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Please read on...and let us know what you think.

Spotlight on Liverpool

Our [recent blog](#) spotlights open research activities at the University of Liverpool and the work of LNL Alexis Makin. The Liverpool Open Research Team have run a highly successful Open Research Week for several years, [this year's event](#) is in late February and will feature several LNLs and a UKRN Roadshow as well as many other events and activities.

Learn how Dorothy Bishop's commentary on the [four horsemen of irreproducibility](#) inspired Alexis to question and audit his own research, and why he now advocates for publishing far fewer papers each containing data from far more participants. There are also his thoughts on increasing trustworthiness, teaching and harnessing the power of UKRN grassroots networks.

Read the full article [here](#)

An activity: run a Reproducibility Tournament

Like Alexis, you could run your own Reproducibility Tournament. This half day event is an engaging way to talk about open research. Invite 10 people to talk about a research challenge that is close to their heart. If anyone else wants to join/speak on the day they can, they don't need to send an abstract ahead of time. Encourage persuasive arguments and solutions rather than just a whinge. Examples at Alexis's event included researchers describing their own activities – this is what I do and why I think others should do it too, that researchers should preregister exploratory analyses of secondary datasets, Alexis's presentation was entitled 'Fewer papers – more participants'. After each talk there is a general discussion. When people give reasons why something can't be done this creates opportunities to discuss those obstacles. Then everyone votes for the most persuasive case. There can be prizes and photos, and it's an opportunity to promote open research across your institution or regionally.

Image credit: Gerd Altmann - Pixabay

Data management

Interested in data management? Join the club! The [ELIXIR Data Management Club](#) provide guidance for life scientists to better manage their research data following the FAIR Principles. It has been developed with funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. They welcome participation from data stewards, support staff and researchers interested in Research Data Management in the life sciences. The club meet over Zoom, on the first Tuesday of every month. Next month's talk is about [BioFAIR](#). These meetings focus on sharing experience and signposting new resources, communities and training. The club also forms a point of contact for a growing pan-European network of data expertise within ELIXIR. The club is growing, please share with your local networks. If you wish to be involved in the group, please sign up for their mailing list.

More information on ELIXIR-UK can be found [here](#).

Dorothy Bishop Prize 2024 - nominations please

Do you know someone doing amazing work to improve open research or promote open research practices? Let the world know, nominate them for the Dorothy Bishop Prize. There will be up to three awards. The winners will each be awarded a prize of £500 (in the form of an Amazon voucher) and a 'Doscar' (a Lego minifigure of Dorothy Bishop). Find out more [here](#)

Closing date: Sunday 28 January 2024

Upcoming events for you...

UKRN Webinar

[Nurturing change through growing UKRN projects](#)

Thursday 18 January 2024 13:00 - 15:00

Making positive change in research culture isn't simple: it needs different strategies and approaches. UKRN is doing just that through a number of new projects. Our first webinar of the New Year is a great opportunity to hear about how we're nurturing changes in research culture through projects that work from the grassroots and across higher-level strategy. Find out how we are harnessing our community and reaching out beyond it, using strategies that range from using narrative theory to meta-research.

Speakers:

Neil Jacobs, Head of the UKRN's Open Research Programme

Anna Ploszajski, UKRN StoryArcs Story Associate

Will Gawned, Community Project Manager

Diane Hird, Community Project Co-ordinator

Lorna Duncan, Research Fellow STAR & METEOR

Rosalind Strang, Project Coordinator STAR & METEOR

ReproducibiliTea online event

Transparent and rigorous political research: rational, context and trends

Wednesday 24 January 2024 14:00 - 15:00

The University of Leeds LNL, Dr Eike Rinke, will be giving an online talk about transparent and rigorous political research. It will explore what openness and transparency can and should mean in this field. Join Eike online here:

Teams meeting ID: 356 425966 308

Passcode: WZuDRo

Our first LNL workshop

[Setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects](#)

Thursday 1st February 11:00 - 12:00

As part of the Community Project we are holding a series of workshops and webinars for LNLs throughout 2024. The first of these will be led by Dr Kait Clark, LNL at the University

of the West of England (UWE) and will be about setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects.

A consortium brings final year undergraduate students and supervisors from several institutions together to work on a shared project. A consortium typically has around 5 supervisors from different universities, each with between 1-8 students (usually 2-5). Kait will present her experience of setting up both mini consortia (projects shared across multiple supervisors within a university) and larger consortia (projects spanning multiple universities). There will be an opportunity for questions and group discussion, followed by the opportunity to begin setting up a new consortium project for the 2024-25 academic year with interested attendees.

The workshop will enable LNLs to learn more about the practical steps involved in setting up internal and external consortia and potentially form a new consortium with fellow LNLs.

All LNLs are warmly invited to attend, whether or not they are involved in student project supervision.

Register here:

<https://bristol-ac-uk.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJYoduugri8pHtHhB7-o9Q1oRt-hhyRFbsNi>

Please also add the following dates and times to your diary for future Community Project events

- Thursday 7th March
- Thursday 4th April
- Thursday 2nd May
- Thursday 13th June

Further details to follow

Save the date - 5th March

**Local Network Leads (LNLs) and Institutional leads (ILs) in-person meeting:
University of Glasgow**

All LNLs are warmly invited to an in-person afternoon meeting (most likely 2 - 4pm) of LNLs and ILs hosted by the University of Glasgow. The event is an opportunity for LNLs and ILs to gain understanding of their respective roles and how UKRN can support these. It will be followed by a reception and dinner. The meeting is open to all LNLs irrespective of whether their institution has an Institutional Lead. UKRN can cover your travel costs and may be able to cover accommodation costs.

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing. Would you like to be a guest editor? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org